

SUCCESSION ISSUES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6581861>

Abdullayeva Hulkar Sobir qizi

Chirchiq davlat pedagogika instituti

Turizm fakulteti xorijiy til va adabiyoti 21/4 guruh talabasi

Abstract: *Foreign languages are taught in all parts of the system of continuing education adopted in our country. One of the most important issues today is to ensure continuity in the teaching of foreign languages between them, for example, at all levels, and to organize teaching at different stages of the system of continuing education with a differentiated approach to the purpose, content, form, methods and techniques.*

Keywords: *succession, education system, levels, teaching, learning, foreign language.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, in the context of globalization, integration and pandemics, global information exchange, joint action in various fields, the study and generalization of experience in these areas remain one of the most pressing issues.

It is known that a foreign language is the most important means of communication in all spheres of international relations. Therefore, foreign language teaching programs, goals, content, methods and forms need to be reviewed and coordinated in accordance with modern requirements.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

By the stages of the system of continuing education, we mean pre-school education, secondary schools, academic lyceums, vocational colleges, technical schools, higher education (institutes and universities), master's education, retraining and advanced training courses.

a) In our country, serious attention is paid to education in preschool

education

institutions (PEI). This can be explained by the structure of the Ministry of Education in this area. If we consider the teaching of foreign languages in PEIs, it also requires a serious approach, because in this educational

institution there are specific features of foreign language teaching, without which it is impossible to effectively organize teaching.

It is known that the main purpose of teaching a foreign language in PEIs is to prepare students for school. The practical purpose of teaching a foreign language in PEIs is to develop children's basic oral speech in a foreign language, to form their skills and to lay the groundwork for learning a foreign language in the future and, of course, to educate them on selected topics. Therefore, what is required of foreign language teachers is to choose foreign language teaching topics with a clear understanding of the purpose of teaching, to find ways to motivate children to learn a foreign language. Depending on the age of the PEI learners, it is advisable to set the lesson time to 25-30 minutes. It is recommended to use a variety of exhibitions (technical and nontechnical), didactic games during the training.

b) Foreign language teaching in secondary schools can be divided into two stages. The first stage can include grades 1-4, and the second stage can include grades 5-11. In our country, teaching foreign languages usually started from the 5th grade. In recent years, the transition from foreign language teaching to first grade has caused problems with textbooks, manuals, and teaching methods. However, now that these problems have been resolved, foreign language textbooks have been created for grades 1-4. In the current situation, it is important to ensure the continuity of teaching materials in foreign language textbooks for grades 1-11. This requires the creation of step-by-step complementary textbooks.

c) The next link in continuing education is academic lyceums, which are

secondary general education institutions that implement continuity and continuity of education. Academic lyceums differ from secondary schools in that they have a large number of hours devoted to certain disciplines, and they can be organized under different universities or separately. They focus on specific areas of social activities and economics, and the disciplines are more closely related to these areas, which is the first step towards training qualified professionals in a particular field in the future. Academic lyceum graduates can take a certain profession in the future, increasing their knowledge in various faculties of colleges, technical schools and universities specific to their field.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is also necessary to take a differential approach to the teaching of foreign languages in philological educational institutions, as there are significant differences between the teaching of foreign languages in the faculties of foreign languages and the teaching of foreign languages in the faculties of Uzbek and Russian.

Foreign language teaching at the faculties of Uzbek and Russian languages is carried out mainly in the form of practical classes. Students of these faculties are required to master a foreign language at the level of professional communication with foreign colleagues. Accordingly, foreign language classes should be organized on the principles of communicative and professional orientation.

In foreign language faculties, a foreign language is taught as a specialty. Therefore, students are taught the language of the specialty in depth, both theoretically and practically. Classes are conducted in the form of lectures, seminars, practical classes, professional skills and competencies are formed at the C1 level of CEFR requirements. At present, textbooks are mainly used for Russian-language universities. One of the most pressing issues today is the development of new curricula and textbooks for Uzbek-speaking students, based on the purpose, content and modern requirements for learning a foreign language.

Summarizing the purpose of teaching foreign languages in non-philological faculties, future specialists trained in these faculties are required to be able to obtain the necessary information in foreign languages from foreign sources, to prepare professional articles, lectures, to communicate with foreign colleagues on professional topics. The educational process should be organized for this purpose. In this case, the development of separate textbooks and manuals in each area of non-philological faculties is one of the most pressing issues today. These textbooks require the selection of professional teaching materials based on the requirements of the time. This mainly includes professional topics, their specific lexical and grammatical material. In our opinion, more attention should be paid to the formation of students' reading, translation and listening skills, as a modern specialist should be able to receive professional information from foreign sources, keep abreast of innovations in this field and apply them in practice.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, foreign language teaching at all levels of continuing education should be in line with the learning objectives at each level, and based on this goal, the choice of teaching content, organizational form, teaching methods and techniques is required. Professional training gives good results when the teachers who organize the training motivate the professionals towards their profession by following these rules.

REFERENCES:

1. Ayatov, R., & Sherov, D. (2020). Improving the Conversational Process in Foreign Language Teaching. *International Engineering Journal for Research and Development*, 5(1), 32-37.
2. Babadjanova, N. (2020). Effective Classroom Management Techniques for Curriculum of 21st Century. *Science and Education*, 1(7).
3. Babadjanova, N., Eshonkulova, S. & Shodiyeva, N. (2020). Using grammar as a factor to enhance practical parts of linguistics. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8 (11), Part II, 185-189.